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Elastic wave mode identification and separation based on piezoelectric and fibre Bragg grating sensors

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Highlights

- Analyses of the difference in elastic wave mode sensitivity of PZT and FBG sensors
- Numerical modelling and experimental investigation
- Novel symmetric and antisymmetric mode separation approach based on mode indicator
- Mode indicator validation based on aluminium and GFRP panel

Abstract

This paper analyses the sensitivity of piezoelectric (PZT) and fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors to propagating elastic wave modes. Elastic waves were excited by PZT actuator and sensed by PZT and FBG sensors. Elastic wave measurements with FBG sensors utilize the edge filtration method. This research conducted a detailed study of the propagation of elastic waves with the modes identification and separation in an aluminium panel. Both numerical simulations as well as experiments were utilized to study the wave propagation and investigate the differences in the sensitivity as well as the opportunity offered by both sensors for mode identification and separation. The numerical simulations were performed using the spectral element method (SEM) in the time domain to capture the spatial and temporal scales involved in the simulation of elastic wave propagation and sensing, especially using FBG sensors. Results showed that the investigated PZT sensor was sensitive to S_0 and A_0 modes, while the FBG sensor was sensitive to S_0 , A_0 , and SH_0 . The FBG senses the SH_0 mode effectively when its propagation is perpendicular to the sensor line. On the other hand, the FBG senses the S_0 mode effectively when its propagation is parallel to the sensor line. This sensitivity feature makes the FBG sensor interesting from the point of view of elastic wave sensing. A novel mode separation method based on the mode indicator was proposed and validated for aluminum samples. The proposed indicator was validated for a GFRP panel with unknown material

properties and dispersion characteristics. It was shown that the proposed methodology could be utilized to distinguish between the symmetric and antisymmetric modes.

Keywords: elastic guided wave propagation; mode separation; FBG sensors; PZT sensors;

1. Introduction

To avoid structural failures and reduce the cost of maintenance, many research studies have been performed to develop damage identification techniques. The corrosion, erosion, fatigue, and impact load are sources of thickness reduction, cracks/notches, and delamination [1]. Today, the elastic wave propagation method is widely utilized in structural health monitoring (SHM). Elastic waves propagating between parallel surfaces are called guided waves. Such waves propagate in plate-like structures and are called Lamb waves. Elastic waves propagate in metallic structures over long distances without significant attenuation. They can be generated as a result of damage initiation or impact load (passive method) or by an actuator (active method). Very often, actuators are made out of piezoelectric material like lead zirconate titanate (PZT). The PZT transducers could be utilized for wave generation as actuators (PZT-A) or wave sensing as sensors (PZT-S). Therefore, they are very attractive from the point of view of continuous damage assessment for SHM. The most popular are the PZT transducers in the form of thin ceramic wafers [2]. Still, they have some disadvantages. Due to electrical signal usage, they cannot be utilized in explosive hazard areas. These actuators are sources of electromagnetic interference (EMI), the operational temperature is limited by Curie point, and the ceramic is brittle. Therefore, more and more attention is focused on the usage of the fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors. They use only optical signals, so they can be utilized in explosive areas and are immune to EMI. Moreover, they can operate at higher temperatures, are flexible, have small mass and diameter, and may be embedded in polymer structures [3], [4]. The advantage of FBG usage in SHM is the possibility of sensor multiplexing, leading to low wiring requirements as well as a low weight penalty. Many FBG sensors could be located on one optical fiber. FBG sensors are utilized for the measurement of static or quasi-static pressure-caused strains in beams [5], pipes and pipelines [6],[7], aircraft landing gear [8], force in bolts [9], dynamic vibration [10], acoustic emission [11], and wave propagation [12]. The FBG sensors are considered as a mature technology for quasi-static strain and temperature sensing. But their application for Lamb wave sensing is still being investigated. The main disadvantage is that FBG works only for sensing (passive) [13], and the amplitude of sensed guided waves depends on the angle of wave propagation with respect to the optical fibre axis (directionality) [3].

The use of FBG sensors for elastic waves sensing has seen an increase in the last few years due to the developments in the field of photonics and acquisition equipment. For the FBG several studies have investigated the unique opportunities that they offer for SHM. Such as the ability to be utilized in the remote configuration [14] where the sensor is not placed on the structure, but the optical fiber is utilized as a mechanical waveguide. This makes it possible to utilize the sensors in extreme environments [15] as well as acoustic coupling, where multiple locations can be sensed using a single sensor [16]. More details of the remote bonding technique may be found in [17]. In addition, another unique feature of the FBG sensors is the ability for

mode filtering using measurements at a single location [18]. The authors have shown that based on the relative ratio of the wavelength of the elastic wave to the gauge length of the FBG the response of the FBG spectrum is different. This can be utilized to perform mode filtering. The authors report that indeed, mode filtering improves the damage localization performance and hence is desired for SHM. Unfortunately, the phenomenon used for the mode filtering is seen in a very limited frequency range for a given structure. Furthermore, the measurement is time consuming, making it slightly less attractive for in-service monitoring. Hence, techniques for mode filtering need to be investigated, which can be performed in near real-time as well as can work in a wide range of frequencies. The multi-modal nature of the elastic waves and their hindrance to SHM is a well-known phenomenon. Fundamental symmetric modes and antisymmetric Lamb wave modes propagate together with shear horizontal modes. Moreover, higher modes could propagate in the structure [19]. Such a multimodal propagation makes the signal processing complex. These problems occur for PZT and FBG sensors. In order to make the results interpretations simpler, the selective wave generation and sensing are performed. The most popular technique is based on the frequency tuning of the wave actuator. Wave generation is performed for such a frequency for which one mode has a significantly larger amplitude than the other [2], [20]. The drawback of such a solution is work for a certain selected frequency. Selective generation of Lamb wave modes is also performed by a special arrangement of actuators. For this purpose, the pair of PZT actuators located at the top and bottom surfaces of the laminate was utilised. The selection of modes was based on the phase of driving signals [21]. The possibility of SH mode excitation by a pair of Electromagnetic Acoustic Transducer (EMAT) was investigated in [22]. The drawback is the need for access from both sides of the structure and precise placement of the transducer pair. Transducers could be spaced with the distance related strictly to wavelength to excite the desired wave mode [23]. This could also be achieved in one transducer with a special distribution of electrodes, like for example in inter digital transducer (IDT), [23], [24], [25]. In this case, mode selectivity is achieved by the special construction of the actuator. Authors of [26] performed Lamb wave mode decomposition based on a special design of the actuator in the form of a concentric ring and circular piezoelectric transducer. The drawback of such approaches is the special design and manufacturing of such transducers. With the FBG sensors, apart from the mode filtering based on the ratio, the polarization maintaining (PM) FBG was proposed for mode filtering. It was shown that the two lobes of the birefringent FBG spectrum have differential sensitivity to the A and S modes. This approach can be utilized for mode filtering, but due to the specialized equipment needed for the PM setup is not considered scalable. Hence, more techniques that are cheaper and easier to implement need to be investigated. One possible solution is the use of symmetrically placed FBG sensors on either side of the sample. This approach has been used for the PZT sensors [21] with some success, but the co-location of the sensors is extremely important, and due to the 2D nature of the PZT transducers, is not easy to implement. The FBG sensors due to their 1D nature, are easier to co-locate and hence are proposed in this paper. Their performance is studied over a large frequency range and compared with the PZT sensors.

The proposed research has its origin in experimental results of analysis of elastic wave signals gathered by PZT and FBG sensors in aluminium panel [27]. Authors of [27] noticed certain wave packages that were registered by the PZT sensor but not by the FBG sensor, and vice versa. However, authors did not identify the types of elastic wave modes. In this paper, numerical simulations were performed to solve this problem. Propagating S_0 , A_0 , and SH_0 modes, as well as mode conversions, were identified based on numerical simulations. For this purpose, the spectral element method in the time domain was utilized. The developed model

includes the model of piezoelectric transducers and the FBG sensor. Experimental results were compared with numerical results. This paper shows that even in such a simple structure in the form of isotropic aluminum panel wavefield is very complex. Also the collocated sensors can differentiate between the modes, based on the phase difference, but when multiple modes are present at the same time the mode identification is non-trivial. For this purpose, we propose the mode separation method based on the mode indicator $MI(t)$, which uses the signal from a pair of sensors located on the top and bottom surfaces of the panel. The idea of such a sensors placement was already used in the literature in the case of PZT or EMAT sensors, but there is research gap for FBG sensors. In this paper, such a sensors configuration is tested for the FBGs. Based on the first part of the research, it is known that PZT and FBG sensors have different sensitivities to guided wave modes. So, we compared the mode separation based on a pair of PZT and FBG. To solve the problem of access to two surfaces of the structure, we propose FBG sensor embedding in the case of a composite plate. We tested the proposed mode separation in the case of two aluminum samples with known dispersion curves and identified propagating mode types. Finally, we tested the proposed indicator for the GFRP panel with unknown dispersion curves and propagating modes. It was shown that the proposed methodology could be utilized to distinguish the symmetric and antisymmetric modes. The development of the metric and the in depth comparison of the FBG and PZT sensitivities for mode separation has not been carried out to the best of the author's knowledge and is the main novelty of the study. Through the thorough understanding of the mode separation performance, solutions may be developed which can improve the damage localization performance of SHM systems.

The paper is organized as follows. We start the analysis of the sensitivity of PZT and FBG sensors related to propagating modes in the isotropic aluminum panel. For this purpose, numerical and experimental investigations are performed. We extracted the modes propagating in the specimen and the sensitivity of both types of sensors. Next, we propose symmetric and antisymmetric mode separation based on pair sensors on the top and bottom surfaces. This methodology was preliminarily tested in two aluminum samples with known dispersion curves and propagating modes for different frequency ranges. Next, we validated the proposed mode separation for the case of the GFRP sample without knowing its dispersion curves.

2. Measurement set-up

Investigations were performed based on numerical simulation and experimental validation. The elastic wave propagation study was performed in the aluminum alloy panel with dimensions 1000 mm × 1000 mm × 1 mm. Elastic waves were generated by a piezoelectric actuator (PZT-A) located in the middle of the panel Fig. 1. Elastic wave sensing was performed by the piezoelectric sensor (PZT-S) and fibre Bragg grating optical strain sensor (FBG). For the FBG, direct bonding was utilised. The PZT and FBG sensors were bonded using cyanoacrylate bonding agent. The distance actuator-sensor was equal to 250 mm. The piezoelectric actuator and sensor were in the form of a disc with a diameter of 10 mm and a thickness of 0.5 mm made out of NCE51 material (CTS corporation - former Noliac). The FBG sensor manufactured by Femto Fibertech with a base length of 10 mm was utilized.

The elastic wave excitation signal was in the form of a toneburst, which allows for concentrating the wave energy in a narrow frequency band. Such signals are commonly utilised in elastic wave propagation research in order to minimise the effect of wave dispersion. In this research electrical signal in the form of five cycles of sine modulated by the Hanning window was generated by the National Instrument PXIe-5413 waveform generator. This signal was

amplified (Krohn-Hite Model 7500) to drive the piezoelectric actuator. The piezoelectric wave sensor was connected to one channel of the National Instrument PXIe-5105 oscilloscope card, which gathered the wave signals. The sampling frequency in the measurement was equal to 5 MHz. In the case of the FBG sensor, the tunable laser (Apex AP1000) was utilized to tune the wavelength on the slope of the FBG sensor (edge filtering) the optical circulator was used to channel the reflected light energy to the photodetector (Menlo Systems, FPD610-FC-NIR). The second channel of the oscilloscope card gathered the electrical signal from the photodetector. Measurements for PZT-S and FBG sensors were performed simultaneously. A signal generator and oscilloscope cards were installed on a personal computer. The process of signal generation and storage was controlled by MATLAB software. For a better understanding of the measurement setup configuration, the paths of optical, electrical, and trigger signals were marked in different colors in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic of measurement setup.

The FBG-based wave sensing was performed using the edge filtration method. The idea of the edge filtration method is presented in Fig. 2. More information about this method could be found in [28], [29].

Fig. 2. Principle of edge filtration method.

3. Numerical model

The numerical model utilized in this work was based on the spectral element method (SEM) in the time domain. The general approach of SEM is similar to conventional FEM. The main difference is related to element node distribution and approximation function describing the displacements. The nodes in spectral elements are not uniformly distributed. The matrices related to finite elements are calculated using the Gauss–Lobatto–Legendre (GLL) integration scheme. The integration points are at the same locations as the element nodes. Due to the orthogonality of shape functions and the utilization of GLL quadrature, the mass matrix is diagonal [30].

The developed SEM model included the host plate, the piezoelectric actuator (PZT-A), the piezoelectric sensor (PZT-S), and the FBG sensor. All components were modelled by the spectral elements based on the 3D elasticity theory of solids, with three displacement degrees of freedom (DOFs) per node and one additional electric-voltage DOF for piezoelectric transducers. The top surface of the PZT actuator/sensor was considered the electrode where the excitation or sensing voltage was applied/recorded, while the bottom PZT actuator/sensor surface was a grounded electrode.

The host plate was discretized using a regular mesh consisting of 250×250 elements (one element per plate thickness) with $6 \times 6 \times 4$ nodes each. The largest distance between nodes (not uniformly distributed) was equal 0.6 mm. The optical fibre with a length of 3990 mm and a diameter of $125 \mu\text{m}$ was divided by 399 sections along, and five elements in-plane of the fibre. Each element had $5 \times 5 \times 9$ nodes. Also, five elements of $6 \times 6 \times 4$ nodes were used to discretize the cross-section of the piezoelectric transducers. The PZT-A, PZT-S, and FBG sensors were attached to the plate using a non-matching interface based on Lagrange multipliers. The SEM model was developed in Matlab using own codes and validated experimentally in [31]. More information about SEM model and the implementation of PZT actuator/sensor and FBG sensor models in SEM can be found in [30] and [31], respectively. The mechanical properties of the simulation components are presented in Table 1.

The data obtained from the simulation contains frames (time step: $dt=5.8651e-07$) of a full wavefield displacement: out-of-plane $S_z(x, y)$ and in-plane $S_{xy}(x, y)$. Displacements were registered on the top surface of the plate for grid $(x, y) = (500 \times 500)$. The values of each array were calculated as follows:

$$S_z(x, y, t) = W(x, y, t) \quad (1)$$

$$S_{xy}(x, y, t) = U(x, y, t)\cos(\theta) + V(x, y, t)\sin(\theta) \quad (2)$$

where: θ is a propagation angle, W is the vector of out-of-plane displacements, U and V are the vectors of displacements in $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$ Directions, respectively. In the simulations, the voltage vector for PZT-S was also obtained. For the FBG sensor response, the displacement vector was defined along the fibre for 101 equally distributed points of the FBG axis of 10 mm length. Then, displacements were converted to the strain vector, and using the transfer matrix method, the FBG sensor response was calculated [32].

Table 1 Mechanical properties of the simulation components

Component	Young modulus		Density	Poisson's ration	
	[GPa]		[kg/m ³]	[-]	
Aluminium plate	71		2700	0.33	
Optical fibre	66		2170	0.15	
PZT	$E_{11}=59$	$E_{33}=47$	7850	$\nu_{12}=0.31$	$\nu_{23}=0.41$

4. Wave modes identification

Numerical results

In the numerical simulation the carrier frequency of the tone burst excitation was equal to 200 kHz. This frequency was chosen to help separate the direct A_0 mode and first reflection of the S_0 mode in the time domain. This allows for avoiding mode mixing and will be further discussed in the section with experimental results.

In the aluminum plate with a thickness of 1 mm, below the frequency 1 MHz, fundamental symmetric (S_0) and antisymmetric (A_0) Lamb wave modes, and fundamental shear horizontal (SH_0) mode propagate. Theoretical group velocities C_g and phase velocities C_p could be calculated using the Vallen Disperse software [33]. Based on the phase velocity and the wave frequency, the wavelength λ could be calculated. In the Tab. 1, the C_g , C_p , and λ for modes A_0 , S_0 , and SH at frequency 200 kHz were presented. The smallest wavelength was observed for A_0 mode (Tab. 1). Based on this value, a mesh of the spectral elements was designed. In our case there is 10 nodes per A_0 wavelength at 200 kHz. While C_p allows for to extraction of the wavelength and distinguishes the modes based on wavelength differences, the C_g allows for time of flight extraction and mode identification based on time of arrivals.

Tab. 1 The group velocities, phase velocities, and wavelength for elastic guided waves with frequency 200 kHz.

	C_g [m/s]	C_p [m/s]	λ [mm]
A₀	2312	1309.4	6.5
SH	3144.2	3144.2	15.7
S₀	5423.3	5429.2	27.1

As a result of the SEM simulation, displacements for nodes over the plate surface are extracted $S(x, y, t)$. The out-of-plane $S_z(x, y, t)$ or in-plane $S_{xy}(x, y, t)$ displacements could be extracted. Having $S_z(x, y, t)$ and $S_{xy}(x, y, t)$ data matrices, the animation of propagating waves could be created.

In Fig. 3a), the selected frame from the animation of wave propagation for $t=0.102$ ms and out-of-plane displacements (eq. 1) is presented. The propagation of fundamental modes S_0 and A_0 is visible. The wave modes were identified based on calculated theoretical group velocities. The mode S_0 has larger velocity than A_0 (Tab. 1). Moreover, both modes have different wavelengths (S_0 is longer than A_0 – Tab.1). The modes can be distinguished observing the wavelength in Fig. 3a), (as distance between valleys). Moreover, the S_0 mode converts to A_0 (S_0/A_0') at the piezoelectric sensor (Fig. 3a). Effect of mode conversion is visible as wavelength change from S_0 to A_0 . In Fig. 3b) a frame for the same time instance for in-plane displacements (eq. 2) was presented. Propagation of S_0 and A_0 modes is visible. The S_0 mode has a larger amplitude for in-plane displacements than for out-of-plane (Fig. 3). This is because the in-plane vibration dominates during S_0 propagation. Moreover, in Fig. 3b) reflection of S_0 mode at PZT sensor (S_0') and conversions of S_0 to SH_0 (S_0/SH_0') and S_0 to A_0 (S_0/A_0') are also visible. The SH_0' mode is visible due to its in-plane displacement vibration character. The modes reflected and converted on PZT sensor were marked with apostrophes in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Frames from the animation of elastic wave propagation at $t=0.102$ ms for displacements: a) out-of-plane, b) in-plane; frequency 200 kHz (numerical results).

In Fig. 4a), a frame for $t=0.15$ ms based on in-plane displacements was presented. It presents the edge-reflected S_0 mode denoted as S_0^1 . There is also a conversion of S_0 to SH_0 at the edge of the plate. The SH_0 mode has a small amplitude in the middle of the wavefront. The modes S_0 and SH_0 could be distinguished by different wavelengths. The SH_0 wave is shorter than the S_0 wave (see Tab. 1 and distance between valleys in Fig. 4a). In Fig. 4b), a time frame based on in-plane displacements for $t=0.264$ ms is presented. The wavefront related to S_0/SH_0 mode reaches the position of FBG and PZT sensors. It should be noted that the mode conversion and propagation can be visualized in the full-wavefield simulation but may not be possible to identify from point measurements at the sensor location alone.

Fig. 4. Frames from the animation of elastic wave propagation for in-plane displacements: a) at $t=0.15$ ms, b) at $t=0.264$ ms; frequency 200 kHz (numerical results).

Besides the displacements S_z and S_{xy} from the simulation of wave propagation, the time signals $s(t)$ gathered by FBG and PZT sensors are extracted. In Fig. 5, the time signals for FBG and PZT sensors are compared. Signals were normalized to unity based on the maximum amplitude in each signal:

$$\hat{s}(t) = \frac{s(t)}{\max|s(t)|}, \quad (3)$$

where: $s(t)$ – raw time signal for PZT or FBG sensor, $\hat{s}(t)$ – signal normalized to unity. The first wave packet is related to the direct arrival of S_0 mode. A good agreement on the first wave packet for FBG and PZT sensors is observed. The second wave packet is related to the directly received A_0 wave mode. The amplitude of this mode is larger for PZT than for FBG sensor. The third wave packet is S_0 mode reflected from the left and right edge and received by sensors (Fig. 4a) at $t \sim 0.150$ ms. Fourth wave packet has an amplitude higher for PZT than for FBG sensor. The fifth wave packet has similar amplitudes for both sensors. However, the sixth, seventh and eighth wave packets are sensed only by FBG sensor. The ninth wavepacket has the same amplitude for PZT and FBG. There are more differences for wave packets later in the signal. This is the effect of different sensitivity of FBG and PZT sensors for different guided wave modes.

Fig. 5. Time signals for FBG and PZT; frequency 200 kHz (numerical results).

Next, the envelope of normalized signal is created. Hilbert transform (HT) is used [34]:

$$\text{HT}[\hat{s}(t)] = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\hat{s}(\tau)}{t-\tau} d\tau \quad (4)$$

This research utilised a discrete version of HT implemented in MATLAB [35]. Next, the envelope of signal is created based on the module of (4):

$$\hat{s}_E(t) = |\text{HT}[\hat{s}(t)]|, \quad (5)$$

where: $\text{H}[\hat{s}(t)]$ – is the Hilbert transform of normalized time signal $\hat{s}(t)$. The signal with envelope for PZT is presented in Fig. 6. Based on animations of wave propagation for in-plane displacements and knowledge about the theoretical group velocity of S_0 and A_0 , subsequent wave packets were identified. The amplitude of S_0 was about 13 times larger than A_0 . The wave packet marked as S_0^1 is S_0 mode reflected from the right edge and sensed by PZT (Fig. 7). Subsequent edge reflected modes are marked with numbers as upper indices. The wave packet S_0^2 is S_0 mode reflected from the top and bottom panel edge (Fig. 7). The packet S_0^3 is related to packet S_0^1 later in the time (as S_0^1 reached the FBG sensor, left edge and later as edge reflected S_0^3 reached PZT sensor - Fig. 7). The S_0^4 is the S_0^3 further in the time for reflection from right edge of plate and propagated back to the PZT sensors (Fig. 7). The S_0^5 is the subsequent reflection of S_0^2 from the top and bottom edge. The S_0^6 is the S_0^4 further in time for reflection from the left edge. There was a lack of SH_0 -related wave packets in the PZT sensor signal (Fig. 5).

Fig. 6. Time signal for PZT sensor with identified wave packets; frequency 200 kHz (numerical results).

Fig. 7. Selected S_0 mode propagation paths for PZT sensing.

Fig. 7 presents the time signal with the envelope gathered by FBG sensor. The first three modes agree with the results for the PZT sensor (Fig. 6). The amplitude of S_0 was about 23 times larger than for A_0 . The wave packet S_0^2 has a significantly smaller amplitude for FBG than for the PZT sensor. This is since the mode S_0 reflected from the top and bottom edge reaches the lateral side of the FBG sensor (Fig. 9). The sensitivity of the FBG sensor is largest if the wave propagates along the FBG axis and lowest at a perpendicular direction [3]. This is visible for S_0 and S_0^1 , which propagate along the FBG sensor direction, and their amplitudes are similar to the PZT sensor. The same situation is for wave packet S_0^3 . The next wave packet was identified as S_0/SH_0 . This wave is visible in Fig. 4a) in time before it reaches the FBG sensor location. This is mode S_0 converted to SH_0 at the top and bottom edge, which reach the FBG sensor (see path from the bottom edge in Fig. 9). The amplitude is large because the

direction of SH_0 propagation is almost perpendicular to FBG sensor, but the vibration direction is nearly parallel to the FBG sensor. It was illustrated for the perfectly perpendicular direction of wave propagation concerning FBG in Fig. 10a) In such a case, the FBG sensor is sensitive to the SH_0 mode but not to the S_0 .

In Fig. 9, S_0 / SH_0 mode conversion on the left edge was indicated (marked in red). However, the FBG sensor did not sense this wave for two reasons. First, it propagates along the axis of the FBG sensor, but the SH_0 in-plane displacements are perpendicular to the direction of wave propagation (Fig. 10b). Second, SH_0 has a small amplitude in the middle of the wavefront (Fig. 4a).

Fig. 8. Time signal for FBG sensor with identified wave packets; frequency 200 kHz (numerical results).

Fig. 9. Selected S_0 and SH_0 mode propagation paths for FBG sensing.

The S_0^4 in Fig. 8 is similar to the result for PZT sensor (Fig. 6). The wavepacket S_0^5 is not visible because this is a further reflection of S_0 , which arrived at the FBG sensor from the lateral side. The S_0^6 is larger than for the PZT sensor and is well sensed by FBG due to the propagation direction along the FBG sensor axis Fig. 10b).

Fig. 10. The S_0 and SH_0 propagating at the direction: a) perpendicular to the FBG sensor, b) along the line of the FBG sensor.

Moreover, there are five other wave packets marked in red as SH_0^* (Fig. 8). Comparisons of the time instances of SH_0^* in the signal (Fig. 8) with time instances from the animation allowed us to notice the fact that the average wavelength of this mode differs from the wavelengths of A_0 and S_0 modes. Therefore, these packets were identified as subsequent reflections of SH_0 . These wave packets were denoted with an asterisk because the total path of propagation is difficult to determine due to the complexity of the wavefield. Fig. 10 presents a wavefield based

on in-plane displacement at $t=0.318$ ms. This is the time instant that the SH_0^* packet reaches the FBG location. There is a second SH_0^* that has already propagated over the FBG sensor location (Fig. 11). It can be noticed that these waves have almost straight fronts marked by lines in Fig. 11. They are the result of wave mode interferences. The time of arrival of the SH_0^* wave packet in Fig. 8 was correlated with time instances in the animation.

Fig. 11. The complexity of wavefield for $t=0.318$ ms.

The most important conclusions based on numerical analysis are as follows. The PZT sensed the S_0 and A_0 , but the sensitivity to S_0 was significantly larger than A_0 for the investigated frequency of 200 kHz. The FBG sensed S_0 , A_0 , and SH_0 . The sensitivity to S_0 is larger when the direction of propagation is along the axis of the FBG and lower when the wave reaches the lateral side of the FBG sensor. The sensitivity to SH_0 is largest when the direction of propagation is perpendicular to the direction of the FBG sensor. The SH_0 is not sensed when its direction of propagation is along the FBG sensor direction. The SH_0 was not identified as generated directly by the actuator. This mode was generated as a consequence of S_0 conversion on the panel edge and at the PZT sensors.

Experimental results

The next part of the research was related to the experimental study. For this purpose, elastic waves in the frequency range 50 kHz – 250 kHz with a step 10 kHz were generated and sensed. Signals for frequency 200 kHz were utilized for the validation of numerical results. In the experiment, more frequencies were utilized for dispersion curves-based mode identification.

In Fig. 12a) numerical and experimental signals for the PZT sensor for frequency 200 kHz are compared. Both signals were normalized to unity. The good agreement of signals for the largest wave packets could be noticed (amplitude of signals and time arrivals). The first wave packet (S_0) has a slightly longer tail for experimental results. There are small wave packets around time $t=0.3$ ms in an experimental signal that do not appear in the numerical results. In Fig. 12b) a similar signal comparison for the FBG sensor is presented. There is good agreement on the amplitude of signals and time arrivals of wave packets. Differences in amplitudes could be observed for the time instance 0.12 ms for A_0 mode. The wave packet in the experimental signal is larger than in the numerical signal. The wave packet in the numerical signal is larger than in the experimental signal. There are some differences also for $t\sim 0.32$ ms for mode SH_0^* (compare with Fig. 8). However, very good agreement is observed for the last four-wave packets.

In the case of experimental FBG and PZT sensors signals (in Fig. 12), there is noise observed before the first wave packet. The FBG sensor itself is immune to electromagnetic interference, but the photodetector is connected to the acquisition card. This path is still influenced by channel crosstalk. Moreover, measurements for PZT and FBG sensors are performed simultaneously for excitation by the PZT actuator.

The good agreement of experimental and numerical results indicates that the simulation result could be utilized for mode identification for the experimental data. The animations of wave propagation based on numerical results are very helpful tools in wave propagation analysis.

Fig. 12. Comparison of numerical and experimental time signals for sensor: a) PZT, b) FBG; frequency 200 kHz.

The next step was related to extracting the experimental dispersion curves. For this purpose, signals from measurements for all investigated frequencies were utilized. First, the theoretical dispersion curves were calculated (Vallen Disperse). Based on theoretical curves and known distance (actuator–sensor), the theoretical time of arrivals of S_0 and A_0 modes were calculated:

$$ToF_T = \frac{L_{A-S}}{C_{gT}}, \quad (6)$$

where: ToF_T – theoretical time of flight for the investigated mode, L_{A-S} – distance actuator – sensor, C_{gT} – theoretical group velocity of propagation of the investigated mode. Next, based on the theoretical time of flight time window with the length the same as the excitation signal is located in the experimental signal. This window starts at the calculated theoretical ToF_T (Fig. 13). Next, the maximum of the windowed $\hat{s}_E(t)$ is found and the time instance t_{max} corresponding to the signal maximum is extracted (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. The idea of experimental ToF extraction.

We need to subtract half of the total excitation signal duration t_{exc} from the t_{max} . This is because ToF is calculated based on the middle of the analyzed wave packet, but not the beginning. The excitation signal duration is calculated based on the formula:

$$t_{exc} = 1/f_m, \quad (7)$$

where: f_m – is the modulation frequency of the tone burst excitation signal. It is calculated based on the known carrier frequency f_c and the number of cycles n_c , of sine in excitation:

$$f_m = f_c/n_c. \quad (8)$$

The experimental time of flight of analysed mode could be calculated using:

$$ToF_E = t_{max} - \frac{t_{exc}}{2}, \quad (9)$$

Next, we can calculate the experimental group velocity based on the formula:

$$Cg_E = \frac{L_{A-S}}{ToF_E}, \quad (10)$$

Repeating this procedure for all frequencies and modes (S_0 and A_0), the experimental group velocity curves are created. This procedure was realized for PZT and FBG sensor signals. In Fig. 14, the theoretical group velocity curves for S_0 , A_0 , and SH_0 were plotted. Moreover, experimentally extracted group velocities for PZT and FBG sensors were marked. In the case of A_0 mode, a better agreement of experimental and numerical data is observed than for S_0 mode. There are some differences in A_0 velocities for frequencies in the range 150-170 kHz.

Fig. 14. Theoretical dispersion curves with marked experimental results.

The dispersion curves in Fig. 14 were related to first first-arriving S_0 and A_0 modes in experimental data. A further step was related to identifying the remaining wave packets in experimental signals based on theoretical dispersion curves. For this purpose, the gathered time signals were plotted in 3D by arranging them in a matrix $\mathbf{S}_F(t)$:

$$\mathbf{S}_F(t) = \begin{bmatrix} s_1(t_1) & \cdots & s_N(t_1) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ s_1(t_M) & \cdots & s_N(t_M) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where: $s_1(t) - s_N(t)$ – time signals for investigated excitation frequency with M time samples, N – number of excitation frequencies ($N=2I$). Time signals with envelopes and absolute values were plotted. The signal for each frequency was normalized to unity based on the maximum value (12).

$$\widehat{\mathbf{S}}_F(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{s}_1(t_1) & \cdots & \hat{s}_N(t_1) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \hat{s}_1(t_M) & \cdots & \hat{s}_N(t_M) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

In Fig. 15, time signals for the frequency range 50-250 kHz seen from the top are presented. On the y-axis, the excitation frequency is presented, while the z-axis presents the amplitudes of the signals.

In Fig. 15a) results for the PZT sensor are presented. In the 3D plot, theoretical time arrivals of S_0 and A_0 were marked. They were calculated for subsequent wave reflection. For this purpose, a previously conducted wave packet analysis for numerical and experimental signals with a frequency of 200 kHz was very useful. In this figure, the identified modes are also marked by symbols. Good agreement of time arrivals and wave packets in the signals is seen. It could be noticed that for the PZT sensor, only the A_0 and S_0 modes were sensed. The S_0 mode has a larger amplitude than A_0 for the frequencies above 100 kHz. For the frequencies below 100 kHz A_0 mode has a larger amplitude. It could be noticed that for 200 kHz, the direct arrived (A_0) and edge reflected S_0^1 modes are separated in time. This was the reason to choose this frequency for the previous numerical analysis. Modes overlapping make the analysis difficult.

Similar results for the FBG sensor are presented in Fig. 15b). In this case, modes: A_0 , S_0 , and SH_0 modes were noticed. Good agreement of time arrivals and S_0 and A_0 wave packets is seen. The S_0 mode has a larger amplitude than A_0 for the frequencies above 110 kHz. In the case of S_0/SH_0 , the theoretical time of arrival is a little bit smaller than for experimental data. For packets marked as SH_0^* , it was impossible to determine the exact propagation path. For the penultimate SH_0^* wave packet, the theoretical time of arrival was marked. It was calculated as the S_0 mode reflection from the top/bottom edge and reflected from the opposite top or bottom edge, and converted to SH_0 . This wave is visible in the animation, but there are more wave packets, and it is hard to determine which one is sensed exactly. However, these wave packets have similar wavelengths, which are related to SH_0 . In this case, the theoretical time of arrival is smaller than the experimental. It needs to be underlined that in the case of SH_0 , its experimental velocity was not validated due to a lack of the packet related to the direct propagation of SH_0 from the actuator to the sensor. So, the experimental value of group velocity could differ slightly from the numerical one.

Fig. 15. The 3D plot of time signals with a theoretical time of arrival of S_0 , A_0 , and SH_0 modes marked, sensor: a) PZT, b) FBG.

Comparing results for PZT and FBG sensors, it could be noticed that there is a wave packet S_0^2 sensed by PZT but not sensed by the FBG sensor. This is because the wave arrives at the FBG sensor from the lateral side. Moreover, SH_0 mode is sensed by FBG but not by the PZT sensor. The A_0 mode is sensed more efficiently than S_0 for low frequencies. Its reflection from edge A_0^1 could be determined based on the theoretical time arrival for low frequencies (Fig. 15). It should be noted, that this analysis of the mode arrival is possible only because the wave velocities and the dispersion characteristics of the wave propagation in the aluminium alloy are known. Application to other structures where the wave propagation is not known is challenging.

Hence mode identification and separation is challenging. Hence new metrics need to be developed which are presented in the next section.

5. Modes separation

In this section, a method for the separation of modes is proposed. In Fig. 16a) experimental signals gathered by two PZT sensors located on the top and bottom side of the panel (at the same x,y position) are presented. The wave frequency was equal to 100 kHz and selected since both A_0 and S_0 modes have large amplitudes then. For the S_0 wave packet, both signals are in phase due to symmetric wave motion with respect to the plate thickness. In the case of A_0 mode, both signals are out of phase. Small differences in amplitudes could be noticed between the two signals. In Fig. 16b) a comparison of signals from a pair of FBG sensors is presented. In the case of FBG sensors, a better agreement of signal amplitudes was achieved than for PZT sensor.

The differences in PZT sensor signals could be caused by the fact that each sensor has additional soldered wires. The mass of the solder could influence the wave sensitivity. The PZT has wrap-around electrodes (both on one side) that are not symmetric, which could also be a source of difference. Moreover, for PZT sensors with a larger area than for FBG sensors, the amount of bonding glue could influence additional sensing results. This needs to be further investigated but is beyond the scope of the current study.

The symmetric mode gives the in-phase wave packets while the antisymmetric out-of-phase. This fact is further utilized for mode separation.

Fig. 16. Signals gathered at the top and bottom side of the panel by sensors: a) PZT, b) FBG; excitation frequency 100 kHz.

Signal addition for a pair of sensors allows for the removal of the antisymmetric modes. In Fig. 17, the results of the addition of signals gathered by a pair of PZT and FBG sensors using (13) were presented.

$$\mathbf{S}_F^{Add} = \mathbf{S}_F^T + \mathbf{S}_F^B, \quad (13)$$

As a result of signal addition, only the wave packets related to symmetric modes are visible. The wave packets related to mode A_0 were removed. In the case of the PZT sensor, only S_0 wave modes are left (Fig. 17a), while for FBG sensor the S_0 and SH_0 are visible (Fig. 17b). It needs to be underlined that a threshold level of 10% of maximum amplitude was applied for better visualization (see color bar). The S_0 modes were marked by solid lines, while SH_0 with lines with square markers. These lines were constructed based on analysis results obtained in the previous section.

Fig. 17. Signal addition for sensor: a) PZT, b) FBG; S_0 (solid line) and SH_0 (square marker) modes marked.

On the other hand, the signal subtraction for a pair of sensors using (14) allows for the removal of the symmetric modes.

$$\mathbf{S}_F^{Sub} = \mathbf{S}_F^T - \mathbf{S}_F^B, \quad (14)$$

In Fig. 18, the results of signal subtraction are presented. The wave packets related to the symmetric mode were removed. Only the antisymmetric mode was left for the PZT sensor (Fig. 18a) and FBG sensor (Fig. 18b) data. This mode was marked by lines with markers.

Fig. 18. Signal subtraction for sensor: a) PZT, b) FBG; A_0 mode marked.

After this simple processing, it was shown that the A_0 mode is sensed up to 140 kHz for the PZT sensor and 150 kHz for the FBG sensor.

Signal summation and subtraction allowed the removal of one mode type: symmetric or antisymmetric. We propose a second method that will enable us to distinguish the symmetric and antisymmetric modes in the gathered data. This method is based on signal multiplication. For this purpose, a mode indicator was introduced:

$$MI_{Raw}(t) = \frac{s^T(t)s^B(t)}{HT[s^T(t)]}, \quad (15)$$

where: $s^T(t)$ and $s^B(t)$ - time signals for top and bottom sensors. Values of this parameter were amplified using HT of the signal in the denominator of (15). The $MI_{Raw}(t)$ for the FBG sensors

for frequency 100 kHz were presented in Fig. 19. The positive values indicate the symmetric mode, while the negative—antisymmetric. However, due to the fluctuation of values of this indicator, it is hard to distinguish the modes. To solve this problem, additional filtration based on moving averages was performed, obtaining $MI(t)$. Moving average filter was based on sliding window with a length of fifty samples. The $MI(t)$ results were presented in Fig. 20.

Fig. 19. Mode indicator $MI_{Raw}(t)$ for FBG sensor signal; frequency 100 kHz.

Fig. 20. Filtered mode indicator $MI(t)$ for FBG sensor signal; frequency 100 kHz.

The $MI(t)$ was utilized for all frequencies, for PZT and FBG sensor signals. Results are presented in Fig. 21. The positive values indicate the symmetric modes and the negative antisymmetric modes. To distinguish the type of modes, A_0 was marked by lines with markers. The proposed $MI(t)$ could be utilized to distinguish the modes without using summation and subtraction separately.

Fig. 21. The $MI(t)$ for sensor: a) PZT, b) FBG; A_0 mode marked

This simple approach showed some possibility of separating propagating symmetric and antisymmetric modes for signal analysis. The proposed $MI(t)$ could be utilized to distinguish the modes without using summation and subtraction separately. Moreover, $MI(t)$ archives positive values for symmetric modes and negative values for antisymmetric modes. This feature could be useful for automated image processing/computer vision because it allows for segmentation the modes based on positive or negative values.

6. Validation of mode separation methodology

Additional specimens were investigated to validate the proposed mode separation methods. The first was another aluminum panel, and the second was a GFRP panel. The further validation was concentrated only on the FBG sensors.

The second aluminum panel

The second aluminum panel had the same dimensions as the first one, presented in Fig. 1. However, new FBG sensors were bonded, and a higher frequency range was investigated (50-500 kHz with a step of 10 kHz).

In Fig. 22 and Fig. 23, the results of the summation and subtraction of signals for FBG sensors are presented. In the case of signal summation, symmetric modes S_0 and SH_0 are left (Fig. 22). In the case of FBG sensors signal subtraction, almost only the antisymmetric mode A_0 is left (Fig. 23). There is the remaining S_0 mode with very small amplitude in two locations.

The $MI(t)$ for FBG signals was presented. The $MI(t)$ works correctly. Moreover, analyzing $MI(t)$ values, it could be noticed that the first arrival of A_0 is also visible for the frequencies above 150 kHz, but its amplitude is significantly smaller than the first arrived S_0 (Fig. 25). The presented results showed that the proposed methodology works correctly for FBG sensors.

Fig. 22. Signal addition for FBG sensors in the second aluminium specimen; S_0 and SH_0 modes marked

Fig. 23. Signal subtraction for FBG sensors in the second aluminium specimen; A_0 mode marked

Fig. 24 The $MI(t)$ for FBG sensors in second aluminium specimen; A_0 mode marked.

Fig. 25. The magnification of Fig. 24 to visualize A_0 visibility.

Glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) panel

The next sample utilized for validation was a GFRP panel with dimensions $0.5\text{ m} \times 0.5\text{ m} \times 0.003\text{ m}$ with embedded FBG sensors. This panel had a symmetric lay-up stack: $[0/45/135/90]_s^\circ$. The specimen was prepared using the vacuum bag process. The PZT excitation was performed by the PZT located in the middle of the panel surface. The FBG sensors were embedded symmetrically between two layers 0° and 45° (the first two – counting from the top side, and the last two from the bottom side). Measurements of elastic waves for excitation frequencies 50-250 kHz (step 10 kHz) were performed. The aim of this investigation was related to the validation of the proposed mode separation methodology. Dispersion curves for this panel were not extracted. However, from the theory of guided waves, it is known that symmetric and antisymmetric modes should propagate in such plates/panels.

The signal summation and subtraction results are presented in Fig. 26 and Fig. 27, respectively. In Fig. 26, the symmetric mode is indicated, while in Fig. 27 antisymmetric. This is also proved by $MI(t)$ results where symmetric and antisymmetric modes are distinguished.

Fig. 26. Signal summation for FBG sensors in GFRP specimen.

Fig. 27. Signal subtraction for FBG sensors in GFRP specimen.

Fig. 28. The $MI(t)$ for FBG sensors in GFRP specimen.

The obtained results showed that simple signal addition and subtraction, as well as the proposed mode indicator $MI(t)$ work correctly for all investigated samples for the FBG sensors. Proposed $MI(t)$ allows us to distinguish both types of modes in one figure. The embedded FBG

sensors in the GFRP plate solve the problem of access to both surfaces, which sometimes is not available.

Conclusions

In this paper, elastic wave mode sensing analysis for PZT and FBG sensors was performed. The simulation of elastic wave propagation based on SEM in the time domain was utilized to identify the wave packets in signals and propagating wave modes sensed by PZT and FBG sensors in the aluminium panel. This allowed to solve the problem of certain wave packages that were registered by the PZT sensor but not by the FBG sensor, and vice versa. For this purpose, the animations of wave propagation for in-plane and out-of-plane displacements were very useful. The animations indicated that the wavefield is very complex, even for such a simple isotropic specimen. The source of such complexity is related to multiple reflections, S_0/A_0 and S_0/SH_0 mode conversions at the PZT, and panel edges and wave interferences. However, what is most important simulations allow for the identification of the wave modes sensed by PZT and FBG sensors. It was shown that PZT senses the fundamental A_0 and S_0 wave modes while FBG senses A_0 , S_0 , and SH_0 . The FBG sensor is sensitive to SH_0 mode when its direction of propagation is not parallel to the sensor line. The inverse situation is for the S_0 mode sensed by FBG. This phenomenon, together with SH_0 mode sensing capability, makes the FBG sensor interesting from the point of view of elastic wave sensing.

Numerical results and theoretical dispersion curves allow for identifying sensed wave packets in experimental signals for frequencies 50-250 kHz. Good agreement of numerical and experimental results was achieved. Experimental results showed that S_0 has a larger amplitude than A_0 for frequencies above 100 kHz for the PZT sensor and above 110 kHz for the FBG sensor.

Moreover, a simple mode separation technique was proposed based on the nature of symmetric and anti-symmetric mode strain distributions. It was possible to separate the symmetric and antisymmetric modes using the pair of sensors placed at the top and bottom. For this purpose, simple signal addition, subtraction, and mode indicator $MI(t)$ were investigated. Proposed mode separation techniques were studied for two aluminum panels with different frequency ranges and a composite GFRP panel. The investigated methodology works correctly for FBG sensors. Due to the 2D nature of the PZT sensors, perfect co-location is not easy to implement. The FBG sensors, due to their 1D nature, are easier to co-locate. This is seen as a very good agreement of signals for the two FBG sensors. The signal summation and subtraction allow only the removal of one type of mode. Other hand, the proposed $MI(t)$ allows for distinguishing the modes without using summation and subtraction separately in one figure. Moreover, $MI(t)$ achieves positive values for symmetric modes and negative values for antisymmetric modes. This feature could be useful for automated image processing/computer vision, because it allows for easy segmentation modes based on positive or negative values. Proposed mode separation is very useful for the process of wavefield analysis like identification of modes for structures without known parameters like in the case of investigated GFRP specimen.

In order to solve the problem with not always available access to both side of structure, sensors embedding in the case of polymer reinforced composite structures like GFRP was proposed and validated.

Further research will be related to using the proposed mode separation methodology for damage detection and localization.

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